

THE USE OF TPR (TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE) METHOD FOR DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ENGLISH CLASSES

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Annotation. *Goal of this article is to look at Total Physical Response (TPR) method as an effective mode for cultivating listening ability in elementary school English class. By looking at the basic notions and techniques of TPR, developed by James Asher and their relationship to language acquisition as a natural process. Teachers of this mode synchronize speech with physical movements in order to immerse students in the learning process. The examination reveals that TPR not only nourishes the ability to receive language communication but also gives rise to an unpressured learning environment which encourages retention long-term for both vocabulary items and grammatical structures. This article also suggests practical exercises like musical games and treasure hunts, that demonstrate in the classroom the application of TPR, realizing its usefulness in training listening abilities. A deeper understanding of the TPR method leads to a better grasp of its role in children's language competence formation and an appreciation for its place in contemporary modern foreign language education.*

Key words. *total physical response, method TPR, listening skills, listening, developing listening.*

One of the popular methods of teaching foreign languages is Total Physical Response. TPR is a language learning method created by James Asher, a professor of psychology at the University of San Jose. It is based on the synchronization of speech and movements. Asher's strategy involves having the students listen to a command in a foreign language and immediately obey with a physical action [2. 13]. Such a reaction makes it possible for students or learners to understand something and still participate in their learning. Listening and responding by doing some activities serves two important functions: it enables the learner to grasp the meaning of a foreign language under study and it makes it possible for a learner to passively acquire grammatical structures. This method makes an implicit presentation of grammatical rules so that the learners may infer them from the linguistic input.

The method falls under the broader comprehension approach to the teaching of a foreign language. Comprehension approach refers to a method of learning a new language through the process of understanding the meaning of words and expressions in the language as opposed to any other form of language learning. Other methods

that may be used as part of the progression of language learning include the process of learning the letters, symbols and other representations of the language first before actually understanding the meaning of the words[4.149]. This emphasis on comprehension before production aligns with the natural process of language acquisition.

Developing Listening skills. In the theory of foreign language teaching methods, the concept of listening was introduced by researcher E.I. Passov. According to his research, listening comprehension is the understanding of speech in a foreign language by ear. In his writings, he suggests distinguishing between the two concepts of listening and listening. The first concept should be understood as listening to the sound shell of a foreign language without understanding the meaning hidden under this shell. By the second concept, E.I. Passov understands precisely the perception of foreign language speech by ear with an understanding of the inherent meaning [3.18]. This distinction is essential, as it highlights that listening is not merely about hearing sounds but involves deeper cognitive processes. It is known that listening is an independent type of speech activity and the fact that it is more difficult than reading and writing is strongly emphasized by scientists. Listening contributes to the achievement of educational goals, gives students the opportunity to understand the text in a foreign language. Therefore, listening is a powerful tool for learning a foreign language, it makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonetic structure and intonation [1.69].

Stages of Listening Comprehension. The first stage of listening comprehension involves the *reception* of auditory stimuli, where the listener perceives sound waves as speech. This phase is governed by the auditory perception system, which detects and processes the sounds of language. Listeners must be able to recognize phonemes, words, and phrases in real-time. Research by Vandergrift highlights that the clarity of acoustic input and the ability of the listener to process the sounds quickly and accurately are essential in this stage.

After receiving the auditory signals, the listener enters the *processing* stage, where they work to make sense of the incoming message. This involves decoding linguistic elements such as words, sentences, and syntax. Listeners draw on their background knowledge, infer meanings, and use context to aid understanding. This active engagement is supported by both *bottom-up* and *top-down* processing models.

- *Bottom-up processing* refers to the listener’s ability to break down the speech into its basic components (e.g., phonemes, words, and phrases) and construct meaning

from the sound itself. It is particularly critical for new or unfamiliar vocabulary [6.67].

- *Top-down processing*, on the other hand, refers to using prior knowledge and expectations to fill in gaps when the linguistic input is incomplete or unclear. It allows the listener to interpret meanings based on contextual clues, discourse structure, and real-world knowledge [5.118].

The final stage of listening comprehension involves *retention*, where the listener stores the information for further processing or future use. This stage is essential for understanding long-term meaning and is related to memory systems. Researchers like O’Malley point out that effective listening comprehension involves not only understanding the immediate message but also organizing and recalling the information after the listening task [5.118].

There was a major difference in how full of energy and lively young learners were as compared to older ones. Classes for such pupils are interactive and instruct students to engage in physical exercises. The teacher or instructor in most of the TPR activities gives commands while the learners respond and perform their responses. After giving a series of orders, the teacher requested the children to consecutively clap hands, stamp your feet, turn around, skip in place, high-five a friend, touch your head, touch your nose, face towards the center, wash your hair or wash your hands.

TPR activities. Using action songs: Singing is always a good tool for learning new vocabulary and highly engaging.

Description: Teach songs that include physical actions, such as 'Head, Shoulders, Knees and Toes.' As students sing, they complete the corresponding movements.

Objective: Combining music with movement promotes listening skills as learning becomes enjoyable.

TPR Scavenger Hunt.

Description: Create a scavenger hunt that allows students to listen to clues about where certain objects or items are located in the classroom or outdoors.

Objective: This reinforces listening and interacts with the environment.

Matching Actions to Words.

Description: Write words or phrases on cards and have the learners match them to actions. For instance, having them match the word 'dance' with an actual dance movement. Objective: This builds comprehension of vocabulary and listening skills when learners connect the words with their physical expressions.

The listening relay race:

Description: Organize a relay race in which students are instructed to carry out a series of actions by listening carefully.

Summary: Total Physical Response (TPR) method is one of the good methods to put into practice in developing listening skills to students in English classes in the elementary school. This technique helps young learners comprehend, retain and engage with the language better by pairing spoken commands with physical actions. Activities practised combined with TPR, such as action songs and interactive games, reinforce listening skills while providing a lively and enjoyable learning atmosphere. In general, TPR is a valuable tool for TFL and offers a warm environment where the students can assimilate the language as they internalize it by moving and doing.

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